

Table S2. Comparative dental measurements in mm of *Galerix rutlandae* and *Galerix wesselsae* M2s from Pakistan and India.

Taxon	Specimen	Locality	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Square root of Area (Size)	Max Width/Max Length (Shape)	Age (Ma)
<i>G. cf. rutlandae</i>	H-GSP 81.14-478	Seh 81.14	1.63	2.25	1.92	0.72	?
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	CH BS 391	CH BS	1.78	2.42	2.08	0.74	?
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	CH BS 392	CH BS	1.63	2.25	1.92	0.72	?
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	H GSP 82.24-47	Seh 82.24	1.8	-	-	-	?
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	H GSP 82.24-48	Seh 82.24	1.85	2.47	2.14	0.75	?
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	H GSP 82.24-53	Seh 82.24	1.78	2.47	2.10	0.72	?
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	H GSP 82.24-54	Seh 82.24	1.6	2.44	1.98	0.66	?
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	H GSP 82.24-55	Seh 82.24	1.7	2.4	2.02	0.71	?
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	H GSP 82.24-56	Seh 82.24	1.56	1.93	1.74	0.81	?
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	H GSP 82.24-59	Seh 82.24	1.78	2.32	2.03	0.77	?
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 24440	Y491	-	-	-	-	13.8
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 24441	Y491	1.8	2.42	2.09	0.74	13.8
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 24442	Y491	-	1.95	-	-	13.8
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 24443	Y491	-	-	-	-	13.8
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 24444	Y491	1.63	-	-	-	13.8
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 24453	Y491	1.8	2.27	2.02	0.79	13.8
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 49040	Y491	-	-	-	-	13.8
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 40027	Y496	-	-	-	-	12.3
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 40029	Y496	-	2.07	-	-	12.3
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 40030	Y496	1.73	2.35	2.02	0.74	12.3
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 40035	Y496	1.83	2.38	2.09	0.77	12.3
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 24445	Y059	1.78	-	-	-	13.6
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 24473	Y059	1.33	1.95	1.61	0.68	13.6
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 24513	Y059	1.53	-	-	-	13.6
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 24479	Y634	1.95	2.25	2.09	0.87	12.3
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 45189	Y634	-	-	-	-	12.3
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 36282	Y640	-	-	-	-	13.6
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 36283	Y640	1.76	-	-	-	13.6
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 36290	Y640	1.89	2.41	2.13	0.78	13.6
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 24427	Y641	1.8	2.17	1.98	0.83	13.7
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 40045	Y641	1.5	2.48	1.93	0.60	13.7
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 24470	Y651	-	-	-	-	13.6
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 24481	Y651	1.58	2.07	1.81	0.76	13.6
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 24507	Y651	1.78	2.32	2.03	0.77	13.6
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 24461	Y660	1.78	-	-	-	13.7
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 24537	Y680	1.65	2.25	1.93	0.73	14.1

<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 34898	Y690	1.7	2.22	1.94	0.77	13.1
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 49005	Y698	-	-	-	-	13
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 17386	Y709	-	2.3	-	-	14.3
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 24518	Y709	-	-	-	-	14.3
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 24529	Y709	1.68	2.35	1.99	0.71	14.3
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 24531	Y709	1.53	2.2	1.83	0.70	14.3
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 24535	Y709	-	-	-	-	14.3
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 40012	Y709	-	-	-	-	14.3
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 34872	Y714	1.78	2.37	2.05	0.75	12.8
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 34874	Y714	-	-	-	-	12.8
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 34878	Y714	-	-	-	-	12.8
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 34879	Y714	1.78	2.3	2.02	0.77	12.8
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 34907	Y718	1.65	2.37	1.98	0.70	13.2
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 34911	Y718	1.63	2.12	1.86	0.77	13.2
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 34912	Y718	1.95	2.37	2.15	0.82	13.2
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 34913	Y718	1.83	2.42	2.10	0.76	13.2
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 34932	Y718	1.63	2.35	1.96	0.69	13.2
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 34934	Y718	-	-	-	-	13.2
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 49021	Y718	-	-	-	-	13.2
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 21830	Y726	-	2.25	-	-	13
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 34861b	Y726	1.75	2.49	2.09	0.70	13
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 34893	Y726	1.85	2.37	2.09	0.78	13
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 48076	Y750	1.76	-	-	-	12.8
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 48077	Y750	1.76	2.41	2.06	0.73	12.8
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 48079	Y750	1.73	2.17	1.94	0.80	12.8
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 48081	Y750	-	-	-	-	12.8
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	YGSP 53937	Y825	1.75	-	-	-	12.7
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	AVERAGE	-	1.72	2.29	1.99	0.75	-
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	MIN	-	1.33	1.93	1.61	0.60	-
<i>G. rutlandae</i>	MAX	-	1.95	2.49	2.15	0.87	-
<i>Galerix sp.</i>	H-GSP 82.24-51	Seh 82.24	1.9	2.57	2.21	0.74	-
<i>Galerix sp.</i>	H-GSP 82.24-52	Seh 82.24	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Galerix sp.</i>	YGSP 39479	Y709	1.8	2.25	2.01	0.80	14.3
<i>G. wesselsae</i>	H-GSP 81.14-4715	Seh 81.14	2.15	2.87	2.48	0.75	-
<i>G. wesselsae</i>	H-GSP 81.14-4716	Seh 81.14	2.15	2.67	2.40	0.81	-
<i>G. wesselsae</i>	H-GSP 81.14a-4307	Seh 81.14a	2.02	2.58	2.28	0.78	-
<i>G. wesselsae</i>	H-GSP 81.14a-4308	Seh 81.14a	2	-	-	-	-
<i>G. wesselsae</i>	H-GSP 81.14a-4310	Seh 81.14a	1.9	2.44	2.15	0.78	-
<i>G. wesselsae</i>	H-GSP 84.24-4250	Seh 84.24	-	1.99	-	-	-
<i>G. wesselsae</i>	H-GSP 84.25-4151	Seh 84.25	1.92	2.58	2.23	0.74	-

<i>G. wesselsae</i>	YGSP 24533	Y709	1.83	2.67	2.21	0.69	14.3
<i>G. wesselsae</i>	YGSP 40046	Y709	-	-	-	-	14.3
<i>G. wesselsae</i>	YGSP 24515	Y747	-	-	-	-	17.8
<i>G. wesselsae</i>	YGSP 48066	Y747	1.89	2.67	2.25	0.71	17.8
<i>G. wesselsae</i>	Z 573	Z122	1.65	2.52	2.04	0.65	18.9
<i>G. wesselsae</i>	Z 617	Z124	-	-	-	-	19
<i>G. wesselsae</i>	AVERAGE	-	1.95	2.55	2.25	0.74	-
<i>G. wesselsae</i>	MIN	-	1.65	1.99	2.04	0.65	-
<i>G. wesselsae</i>	MAX	-	2.15	2.87	2.48	0.81	-
<i>Galerix sp.</i> indet.	VPLJU/LSKM/84	Ramnagar (K2, Kulwanta)	1.9	2.5	2.18	0.76	-

Notes: Max Width = maximum width, Max Length = maximum length. Area = Max Width x Max Length. Comparative measurements taken from Zijlstra and Flynn (2015) and the current study.